

1 **CDK4 is activated in lung metastasis in human breast cancer.**

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6 We report here the identification of CDK4 as a viable therapeutic target in human breast cancer
7 featuring metastasis to the lung. CDK4 was retrieved as an up-regulated and differentially expressed kinase in
8 lung metastasis using whole transcriptome technology that measures and compares total transcription in human
9 breast cancers (the primary tumor) and in the lung metastases of humans with metastatic breast cancer.
10 Recurrence-free survival was superior in breast cancer patients whose tumors expressed low levels of CDK4,
11 indicating pharmacologic inhibition of CDK4 that mirrors (endogenous) low CDK4 tumor expression confers
12 an RFS benefit in this patient population. We recently demonstrated using multiple whole transcriptome
13 technologies a likely and strong therapeutic benefit in humans with hormone receptor positive (HR+) cancer
14 (luminal A and luminal B subtypes) in conferring a protective effect against CNS disease. These data indicate
15 patients with existing lung metastasis are also likely to benefit from adjunctive pharmacologic CDK4/6
16 inhibition from the -ciclib family (palbociclib, ribociclib and abemaciclib), and that adjunctive CDK4/6
17 inhibitor likely confers a protective effect against development of lung metastasis in metastatic breast cancer in
18 patients who have not yet progressed.
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Figure 1: CDK4 is differentially expressed and up-regulated in the lung metastases of humans with metastatic breast cancer.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1019	7.27E-03	0.46	-2.68415	-1.2348155	2310.51	CDK4	1661/22997	92.8

Figure 2: Recurrence-free survival in humans with breast cancer is superior in patients with low CDK4 tumor expression.

Chart 1: Recurrence-free survival in humans with breast cancer is superior in patients with low CDK4 tumor expression.

High expression: 71 months (median)

Low expression: 34.52 months (median)

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Methods

We utilized RNA-sequencing from GSE191230 (*n*=6 primary tumors (breast tumors from humans with breast cancer) vs. *n*=2 lung metastases (lung metastases from humans with breast cancer) for this study. We used human survival data from *n*=4929 humans with breast cancer for this study. We used survival data (RFS in months) generated using a Q1 vs. Q4 option.